

The PINK Objectives

1. Develop innovative modelling and simulation approaches addressing industrial SSbD needs.
2. Make the software accessible to SMEs and industry through an open innovation platform.
3. Validate the platform on PINK Developmental Case Studies and Industrial Demonstrators provided by SMEs and large industries.
4. Fully implement open science and FAIR principles contributing to establishing a European chemicals and materials data, modelling and software ecosystem.
5. Strengthen knowledge transfer through collaboration and exploiting synergies.
6. Boost the innovative capacity of SMEs and industry and make them more agile to respond to external and internal influences.

The PINK tiered Approach

In the PINK tiered Approach, each development cycle will start with mining and creating data on the functionality, safety, and sustainability, as well as cost/economic feasibility; these form the simultaneous input for the decision support workflow. (cf. EU SSbD Framework (left) vs the PINK *In Silico* Hub (right)).

> PINK

Provision of Integrated Computational Approaches for Addressing New Market Goals for the Introduction of Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design Chemicals and Materials

The **PINK** Project combines **computational models** and a **decision support system (DSS)** that **exploit the combined power of first-principles simulation and pre-existing data**, which – in itself – is further improved by **advanced artificial intelligence (AI)** technology; this provides PINK with the capability to significantly decrease the time needed for SSbD AdMas&Chems development.

The PINK R&I Approach

The **integration of the SSbD Framework into the development cycle of AdMas&Chems** (lower part) will be achieved by **solving the multi-objective optimisation problem** to improve and balance the four requirement categories (i.e. functionality, cost-efficiency, safety and sustainability, middle part) at each stage of the development.

This will be achieved by integrating existing data and filling data gaps using innovative modelling and simulation approaches from the complete life cycle and value chain (upper part). All five steps of the SSbD will be integrated in each stage, even if starting with a limited set of evaluation criteria or rough estimates for each step at early development. PINK will then be able to use **higher-tiered methods in later material development stages**, providing **higher confidence in the predictions** by producing increasing information on a constantly reduced set of better performing candidates.

PINK will **push current boundaries of the integration of computational approaches in the development of SSbD AdMas&Chems in industry and especially SMEs**, based on the amalgamation of different technologies into intelligent, tiered functionality, safety and sustainability evaluation and assessment approaches that address market-relevant AdMas&Chems at all stages of their lifecycle and along the complete value chain.

Industry readiness of the solution will be guaranteed by improving usability, practicability, user experience, and 'data provenance' documentation and security and integrate these as important aspects into the development of new modelling software and decision support services.

@PINK-Project

www.PINK-Project.org

PINK has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101137809. Associated

Partners from (a) Switzerland, and (b) United Kingdom, received national funding from (a) the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), and (b) Innovate UK (UKRI).

